

70%), m.p. 165° (Found: C, 54.33; H, 2.53; N, 18.89. C₁₀H₆ON₃Cl requires: C, 54.79; H, 2.74; N, 19.18%).

2-p-Chlorophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole⁵: A mixture of 2-p-chlorophenyl-5-cyanomethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5 g) 10%, NaOH solution (80 ml) and alcohol (15 ml) was boiled under reflux for 1 h and then boiled for a few minutes in the open flask. It was then cooled and concentrated HCl added until the precipitation of the acid was complete, (4.5 g, 83%), m.p. 200° (Found: C, 50.33; H, 2.85; N, 11.63. C₁₀H₇O₃N₃Cl requires: C, 50.42; H, 2.94; N, 11.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3100–2500br (OH), 1690 (C=O), 1550 (O=C–O), 1590 (C=N) and 1090 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C).

N'-Phenyl-N³-2-p-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylacylurea⁶: A mixture of 2-p-chlorophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.05 mol), dioxane (20 ml) and thionylchloride (5 ml) was heated under reflux at 70–80° for 6 h. The excess thionylchloride was then removed by distillation and the product was refluxed with phenylurea (0.01 mol) in dioxane (15 ml) for further 6 h. The contents were poured in ice-water and the excess phenylurea and acid was removed by treatment with boiling water and sodium hydroxide respectively, (0.9 g, 75%) (Found: C, 57.08; H, 3.21; N, 15.68. C₁₇H₁₃O₃N₄Cl requires: C, 57.3; H, 3.65; N, 15.73%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1680 (CONHCO), 1620 (C=N), 1540 (N–H def. + C–N str.), 1090 (C–O–C) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 6.84–8.07 (9 H, m, ArH), 3.25 (H, s, OCH₂) and 8.88 (2H, s, NHCONH); m/z 52, 65, 80, 92, 95, 109, 123, (base peak) 134, (McLafferty rearrangement) 139 and 272.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening was carried out using cup-plate⁷ method against gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 50 µg. All the compounds showed moderate antimicrobial activity; however, compound bearing R=*o*-tolyl showed highest activity against *S. aureus* (23 mm). It was observed that fungi *A. niger* and *S. cerevisiae* were moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

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Synthesis of 2-Hydroxy-4,6-diphenylpyrimidines and their Antimicrobial Activity†

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PYRIMIDINE derivatives are known to possess various biological activities¹. This initiated us to synthesise the title compounds and evaluate their possible antimicrobial activity.

Literature survey reveals that the synthesis of title compounds have not been undertaken. The 2-hydroxy-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidines were obtained by the cycloaddition² of an appropriate 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (3) with urea in presence of ethylene glycol as solvent. Use of dimethylformamide in place of glycol gave poor yields.

†The paper was presented in the 75th Session of the Indian Science Congress.

These synthetic pyrimidines have been tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Sarcina lutea* and *Escherchia coli*.⁶

The structure of the compounds synthesised were supported by their spectral study. The compounds prepared are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield %	M.p. °C
4a	H	H	H	60	95
4b	H	CH ₃	H	70	112
4c	H	Cl	H	70	175
4d	Br	CH ₃	H	60	168
4e	Br	Cl	H	60	165
4f	H	H	OCH ₃	55	142
4g	H	CH ₃	OCH ₃	80	155
4h	H	Cl	OCH ₃	70	170
4i	Br	CH ₃	OCH ₃	60	178
4j	Br	Cl	OCH ₃	60	152

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. All the 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethanes used as starting material were prepared according to the known methods⁵.

O-Aryloxyacetophenone (2): O-Aryloxyacetophenone (2a-e) was prepared from 2-hydroxyacetophenone (1) using benzoylchloride (Schotten-Baumann reaction).

O-Aryloxyacetophenone (2f-j): 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 mol) and anisic acid (0.12 mol) were dissolved in dry pyridine (60 ml). The solution was kept in cold water-bath and phosphorous oxychloride (0.07 mol) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring and external cooling—the temperature being maintained below 50° throughout. After 3 h the mixture was decomposed by cold 1 : 1 dilute HCl (till the solution was acidic to congo red paper) and the white product was filtered and washed with water and 10% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove unreacted anisic acid. The solid was crystallised from rectified spirit to get 2f-j. Their alcoholic solution did not give colour reaction with FeCl₃ solution.

2'-Hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane (3a-j): O-Aryloxyacetophenone (2a-j) (0.05 mol) was dissolved in dry pyridine (30 ml). The solution was warmed and added to molten KOH (0.15 mol) with stirring. The solution was stirred for 2 h and kept overnight. The resulting solid was decomposed by adding cold dilute HCl (1 : 1) until the reaction mixture was acidic. The yellow solid was filtered, washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and with water. The lemon-yellow product (3a-j) was crystallised from rectified spirit.

2-Hydroxy-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (4a-j): A mixture of 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (0.01 mol) and urea (0.01 mol) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The product was filtered and washed with water and dried at 80° and crystallised from ethanol to get 4a-j.

Biological activity: The biological activity was evaluated by the usual filter paper disc technique. The title compounds (4a-j) were tested against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. lutea* and *E. coli*. Compounds 4h-j were found inactive against the said organisms. Compound 4a showed a very strong inhibition against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* whereas 4d showed moderate activity against *S. aureus* and *S. lutea*. Compounds 4b-g showed moderate or weak activity against all the said organisms. The biological activity of the title compounds are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA* OF COMPOUNDS 4

Organisms	4a	4b	4c	4d	4e	4f	4g	4h	4i	4j
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	-	++	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>B. subtilis</i>	++++	+++	+++	++	+++	++	+	-	-	-
<i>S. lutea</i>	+++	+	+	+++	+++	+	-	-	-	-
<i>E. coli</i>	++++	+++	+	-	+	++	+	-	-	-

*(++++), (+++) = High potency, (++) = medium potency, (+) = low potency, (-) = no potency.

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Nitrofurfuraldehyde as-Triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazones

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A number of as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles are reported to possess antiviral, analgesic and hypertensive properties¹⁻⁴. Prompted by the pharmacological importance of triazinoindoles and as a part of our

general search for pharmacologically active nitrofuran compounds^{5,6}, we report herein the synthesis and biological activities of some substituted-nitrofurfuraldehyde as-triazino-indolyl hydrazones.

The reaction of substituted-isatins and thio-semicarbazide provides a convenient method for the synthesis of 3-mercapto-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles⁷. These mercapto compounds on hydrazinolysis yielded as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazines (1) which are characterised by elemental analysis. These indolylhydrazines when condensed with nitrofurfural diacetate in alcohol medium using concentrated sulphuric acid as catalyst yielded the required nitrofurfuraldehyde hydrazones (2). The structures of these compounds are confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and mass spectral data (Table 1).

All the new compounds were analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N. Fairly intense to weak molecular ion peaks were observed in the mass spectra of these hydrazones. In all cases fragment peaks were also observed corresponding to ions obtained by the loss of NO₂ and CO from the molecular ions.

Antibacterial activities of nitrofurfuraldehyde hydrazones (2a-j) determined against *S. aureus*, *A. aerogenes*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* by disc-diffusion method, revealed that 2c possessing dichloro substitution at the benzene ring has antibacterial activity comparable to that of furacin. The antibacterial activities of the compounds diminished when the indole NH was alkylated by methyl and ethyl substituents

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a-j

Compd. R	R ¹	Yield %	M.p. °C	Molecular formula*	ν _{max} (nujol; cm ⁻¹)		M ⁺	m/z (% abundance)	
					NO ₂	NH		M-NO ₂	M-NO ₂ -CO
2a	H	H	>360	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	Too weak	323 (49.5)	277 (100)	249 (61.2)
2b	H	8-Chloro	215-17	C ₁₄ H ₈ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m	357/359 (20.5)	311 (26.8)	283 (25.6)
2c	H	6,8-Dichloro	284-85	C ₁₄ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 650w			
2d	H	8-Methyl	304-05	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 520	3 550w	337 (18.4)	291 (26.3)	263 (21.3)
2e	Methyl	H	295-96	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂	1 375, 1 520	Too weak	337 (90.2)	291 (100)	263 (51.0)
2f	Ethyl	H	264-66	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	Too weak			
2g	Methyl	8-Chloro	316-18	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m			
2h	Ethyl	8-Chloro	322-25	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m			
2i	Methyl	8-Methyl	270-72	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m	351 (24.8)	305 (100)	277 (46.3)
2j	Methyl	6-8-Dichloro	307-08	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₇ O ₂	1 375, 1 540	3 500w			

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.